

Example Chimpanzee Ethogram and Data Recording Instructions
The Kibale Chimpanzee Project and the Cognitive Evolution Group

General instructions:

- The idea of focal observations is that a focal individual is randomly chosen and then their behavior is recorded for a specific period in a consistent, reliable way.
- These examples use 10 minute focal observations but you can adjust the length of time to suit your particular study question
- You should make sure you have a system to distribute your observation effort approximately equally across individuals, and to ensure that you are not choosing individuals to focal because they are doing something interesting when you start the observations

Focal behavior scans: Scan sampling is a [method](#) that helps capture a picture of what animals do across a normal day. By *recording whatever activity an animal is doing at a specific time interval*, this method is particularly useful to help observers reduce biasing data toward animals' most interesting and/or obvious behaviors (for more detail, see [Altmann 1974](#)). You can record behaviors at whatever time interval is best for your study, but here we use 2 minutes.

- You should complete a scan at the beginning of the 10 minute period, and then every 2 minutes for a total of 6 scans.
- For each scan, write down what the chimp is doing at that moment. This makes it possible to compare their rates of different behaviors. You should only look at behaviors of the focal during the 10 min period—when this period ends you should stop.
- *Protip: Use a stopwatch or a timer app on your phone to make sure you record scans at exactly 2-minute intervals.*

Filling out the focal behavior table: Please follow the instructions below to fill out each column in each row of the focal behavior table.

- *Scan time:* Indicate hour and minute of that scan; should occur every 2 minutes
- *Focal behavior:* create and use an ethogram of appropriate behaviors for your study. Ethograms include a list of behaviors and their *operational definitions*, or the specific definitions that you and other observers should use to identify and categorize those behaviors in your study. This list does not need to include every behavior used by a given species, but *should include all of the behaviors that are important for answering your research question*. Here is an example ethogram for chimpanzees:
 - **GROOM** = grooming or being groomed, include the direction of the grooming in the comments section (*make sure to fill out the all-occurrence focal grooming table too*)
 - **PLAY** = tickling or wrestling with another chimp in a positive interaction (e.g. may see play face or hear laughter) or playing solo. This would also include play with a stick or some other object.
 - **FEED** = eating food or actively searching for food (e.g. picking through bits on the ground)
 - **TRAVEL** = moving or walking that is not aggression, play, or searching for food
 - **REST** = not traveling, not grooming
 - **OTHER** = something that we have not defined here; please describe in detail in the comments what the chimpanzee is doing
 - **OUT OF VIEW (OOV)** = the focal individual cannot be seen at the time of the 2 min scan. Please note that focals *must* be visible at the start of the scan.
- *ID2 if social:* Name of the other chimpanzee in interaction if the focal is grooming, playing, or involved in aggression. If play is solo, write "solo" in ID box. If you cannot tell who the partner is, write "unknown."

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- *All IDs within 1m of focal:* All chimpanzees in 5 meters to the focal at time of scan. This allows you to reconstruct who that individual sits and spends time near. Depending on your study population, you may modify what a useful distance is.
- *Comments:* any description or other comments that will help explain what the focal was doing. Some examples:
 - Describe social interactions like play in more detail (“Kelly was playing with David by tickling and softly biting David’s fingers,” or “Quentin and Wolfgang were wrestling roughly and laughing”);
 - Provide additional details about aggression (“Leonard attacked Lillith who was in estrus but also eating, so the context was unclear,” or “Before Leonard attacked Lillith, he was a victim of Scar’s. Then he attacked Lillith with bites and slaps.”);
 - You can also use this space to record things that aren’t captured elsewhere in the datasheet but you may want to remember later (“Ollie was feeding, but kept getting distracted by how sticky the fruit was”)

All-occurrence sampling: Some behaviors that might be very interesting and/or obvious are also rare. These behaviors might not be accurately or adequately captured using scan sampling because rare behaviors are less likely to be “caught” on the beep of the timer. For these behaviors, it is sometimes better to use an all-occurrence sampling method where the observer *records every instance* of a particular behavior that they see (for more detail, see [Altmann 1974](#)). Social behaviors and interactions are good examples of this type of rare, but important behavior.

- **Use all-occurrence sampling to record grooming, aggression, pant grunts, and tool use.**
- This should include any of the above behaviors that are performed by or with the focal, *even if it is not at the 2 min focal scan times*. This should be a complete picture of all the focal’s grooming, aggression, and tool use over the 10 minute period. If the focal spends the whole 10 minutes grooming, then the box should show this.
- Sometimes, a behavior that you record all-occurrences of will *also* happen on the beep for your instantaneous scan. In these cases, *be sure to record the behavior in both tables*.

Focal Grooming (only grooming with focal – for each row should be an event of a grooming bout).

Please use the following instructions to fill out each column of each row of the grooming table:

- *Bout #:* A new bout number / row begins if significant time (>2 mins) elapses between grooming behaviors, if a new individual begins grooming the focal, if the focal begins grooming a new individual, or if the direction of grooming switches (for example, if chimp A is first grooming chimp B and then chimp B starts grooming chimp A instead).
- *Start time:* Hour and minute the grooming bout started. Write “in progress” if they were already grooming when you started the 10 min focal
- *End time:* Hour and minute the grooming bout ends; Write “in progress” if they were still grooming when you ended the 10min focal
- *Partner ID:* Name of the chimp(s) that the focal is grooming or being groomed by
- *Direction & Chain Grooming:* Indicate which chimpanzee groomed who by using arrows (e.g. A→B means A was grooming B). If was there more than a pair involved in the grooming bout (chain grooming) use sequence of arrows between IDs to note who was grooming who (e.g. A→B→C means A was grooming B who was grooming C).
- *Comments:* Any other interesting things to note can go here. (e.g. “Quentin had a piece of fruit stuck in their hair,” “John and Danny were grooming and Joffry broke it up by displaying toward them”)

Example Chimpanzee Ethogram and Data Recording Instructions
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- If the focal is part of a big group with many individuals grooming each other you can also provide a small drawing of everyone's location and mark the grooming directions with arrows

Focal Aggression (only aggression with focal – each row should be an event). For chimpanzees, aggression is an important part of daily social life (see Modules 1 and 4). Please use the following instructions to fill out each column of each row in the aggression table:

- *Time:* Hour and minute the aggression happened
- *Aggressor ID:* Which individual did the aggression?
- *Type of aggression:* Here we specify three types or levels of aggression, but your study might want more detailed categories for different intensities depending on your question
 - **DISPLAY** = chimpanzee displays by throwing something and/or making noise, but there is no other specific chimpanzee who is the victim or target of the aggression
 - **THREAT** = one chimpanzee threatens, lunges at, charges, chases, or displays at another without making physical contact
 - **ATTACK** = one chimpanzee hits, kicks, or bites another with physical contact
- *Victim ID:* Who was aggressed? Identity of the chimpanzee who was threatened, chased, or attacked. If the aggression type was a DISPLAY, there is no victim.
- *Victim response:*
 - **NEUTRAL** = does not submit or aggress
 - **SUBMITS** = screams, pant-grunts, flees, walks away, or otherwise avoids the aggressor
 - **RETALIATE** = attacks original aggressor
 - **REDIRECT** = attacks someone other than the original aggressor (say who)
 - **REASSURANCE** = approaches another chimpanzee for friendly contact (say who)
- *Coalition:* did other individuals support either the aggressor or victim? If so, say who supported who
- *Context and comments:* Describe the aggression and note if the fight occurred over food, over a swollen female (mating), protecting a juvenile, or for another reason. If a clear context cannot be determined, write unknown.

Pant grunts and pant barks (all occurrences that involve the focal). Pant-grunts and pant parks are vocalizations that chimpanzees make to signal their subordination (e.g. that they are lower-ranking) to another group member (see Modules 1 and 5 for examples). These vocalizations can be used to determine the ranking order of all of the adults in a social group. Please use the following instructions to fill out each column of each row in the aggression table:

- *Time:* Hour and minute the pant grunt/bark (specific vocalization) happened
- *Vocalizer ID:* Which individual made the pant grunt/bark?
- *Recipient ID:* Which individual did they pant grunt/bark towards?
- *Context and comments:* Note if the pant grunt/bark occurred during a contest over food, over a swollen female (mating), protecting a juvenile, or for another reason (e.g. "Edwin made pant-barks to Eragon as they both approached the feeding tree," "Algernon joined the party and approached pant-grunting to Beaufort.")

Object / Tool Use (all occurrences that involve the focal). One of Jane Goodall's most important findings is that, like humans, chimpanzees use tools! Please use the following instructions to fill out each column of each row in the tool-use table:

Example Chimpanzee Ethogram and Data Recording Instructions
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- *Time:* Hour and minute the tool use started
- *Material:* Indicate the type of tool (stick, rock, leaf, etc.)
- *Description:* describe what the chimpanzee did, e.g. "Afiya used a stick to obtain food by inserting it into a hole" or "Banji used a rock to crack open a nut."

- When you describe what the chimpanzee did, be sure to enter all behaviors in which an object is manipulated. Here we specify some possible types, but your study might want more detailed categories depending on your question
 - Using a **STICK**, such as to poke something or to fish for insects
 - Using a **WEAPON** such as a stick or rock to hit or throw at another chimpanzee (e.g. also as a display).
 - Using a **TOY** such as a stick or a rock when playing with another chimpanzee or by themselves

- Chimpanzees may use objects or tools in a number of different contexts. Be sure to make notes about how the object was used. Here are some example contexts:
 - **FORAGING:** e.g. using a stick to fish for insects or honey
 - **AGGRESSION:** e.g. using a stick or stone to hit or throw at another chimpanzee, or during display
 - **PLAY:** carrying or using an object when playing with another chimpanzee or by themselves (e.g. throwing a stick or a stone up in the air and catching, rolling it in the hands)
 - **CLEANING:** using leaves or sticks to clean a body part (e.g. when having a wound)
 - **CARRYING / HOLDING:** sometimes chimpanzees might pick up an object that isn't food and simply take it with them or hold it in their hands, or in the gap between their thigh and their belly (sometimes called a "hip pocket").